

Fig1

Fig2

A

B

C

D

E

F

Fig3

A

B

C

D

E

F

Fig4

A

B

C

D

E

F

Fig5

A

B

C

D

E

F

Fig6

A

Sequencing saturation curve of WT1

B

Sequencing saturation curve of WT2

C

Sequencing saturation curve of WT3

D

Sequencing saturation curve of KO1

E

Sequencing saturation curve of KO2

F

Sequencing saturation curve of KO3

